

Digitalisation Dialectics in Religious Preaching: Analysis of Religious Communication Transformation in The Digital Era

Nikolaus Kristian Badu Ratu¹, Aloysius Liliweri², and Blajan Konradus³

^{1,2,3}University of Nusa Cendana, Kupang, NTT

ABSTRACT

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This study aims to examine the transformation of religious communication in the context of digitalization, focusing on the practice of digital preaching in the Archdiocese of Ende. Using a qualitative approach and critical paradigm, this study explores how the dynamics of preaching have changed due to the penetration of digital technology into the religious life of the Catholic community. The case study method is used to understand the local and cultural context in the preaching process, involving data collection techniques in the form of in-depth interviews, participatory observation, documentation, and digital content analysis. The results of the study show that digitalization has influenced the way preachers convey messages of faith, expanded the reach of audiences, and created new spaces for interaction between preachers and the congregation. However, this transformation also presents challenges, such as the loss of depth of personal relationships, the emergence of disinformation, and fragmentation of understanding of faith. This study highlights the importance of critical reflection on digital media as a means of preaching, as well as the need for contextual and participatory communicative strategies so that religious messages remain authentic and relevant. In the context of the Archdiocese of Ende, digital preaching is not only a technological adaptation, but also a form of cultural and theological dialectic that reflects changes in the social and religious structure of the congregation. This research contributes to the study of religious communication and encourages the church to continue to strengthen digital literacy in preaching for the sustainability of faith in the digital era.

KEYWORDS:

Digitalization, Catholic Church, Communication, Proclamation, Transformation

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of digital technology has created a major transformation in various aspects of human life, including in the religious field. The COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated this process of change by forcing various institutions, including religious institutions, to shift activities that were previously carried out physically to digital spaces. The Catholic Church, as an institution that has a long tradition of direct and conventional preaching, is faced with a major challenge to maintain its existence in the midst of a dynamic digital era. Various digital platforms such as YouTube, Zoom, and other social media have begun to be used intensively as a means of communication and preaching the faith to the people.

Corresponding Author: Nikolaus Kristian Badu Ratu

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In the Archdiocese of Ende, the use of digital channels such as Komsos KAE and Komsos SVD are concrete examples of how the Church has begun to adopt technology as an integral part of its ministry.

However, this transformation has not been without friction. On the one hand, digitalization has opened up opportunities for the Church to reach more people quickly and efficiently. On the other hand, tensions have emerged between the traditional approach to preaching, which is full of spiritual and cultural values, and digital methods that demand efficiency and rapid adaptation to technological developments. This dialectic not only reflects changes in the technical aspects of communication, but also involves issues of identity, religious values, and internal resistance from more conservative groups within the Church. This transformation has even invited philosophical debates about the authenticity of religious messages and the challenges of maintaining spirituality amidst the flow of digital information that is often secular and pragmatic.

Nikolaus Kristian B.R. et al, Digitalisation Dialectics in Religious Preaching: Analysis of Religious Communication Transformation in The Digital Era

This study specifically focuses on the dialectics that emerge in the process of digitalization of preaching in the Catholic Church of the Archdiocese of Ende, by examining how digital channels such as YouTube Komsos KAE and Komsos SVD are used as a means of preaching. The main question to be answered is: How does the dialectic of digitalization in religious preaching transform religious communication in the technological era? The purpose of this study is to analyze the process of transformation, including the dynamics of interaction between traditional religious values and modern digital approaches. By understanding this dialectic, this study is expected to provide a strategic contribution to the Church in managing the digital adaptation process without losing its spiritual depth and religious identity.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of dialectics used here refers to Hegel's understanding of dialectics. According to him, dialectics is a process in which two opposing ideas are brought together to produce a new, more comprehensive understanding (Bertand Russel, 2024). Simply put, in the framework of Hegel's dialectics, this concept involves three main stages: thesis (initial or pro view), antithesis (opposite or contra view), and synthesis (new understanding that summarizes both views).

Digitalization itself is related to the process of transition in the use of analog media (conventional media) to digital media (for example internet-based media such as websites, Facebook, WhatsApp or YouTube). According to Baym, G., & Donsbach, W. (2008), digitalization is seen as the process of encoding signals as numbers. This process is at the heart of modern technology, as it allows data to be stored, accessed, and communicated with high speed and accuracy.

One important aspect in digitalization and religious institutions is the changing pattern of preaching. Preaching in the concept of the Church can be interpreted as an activity of conveying the gospel based on the teachings of Christ. This preaching aims to bring about profound changes in humans and renew their lives. in the document *Lumen Gentium* (Church Document Series, J. Hadiwikarta trans. 2019) preaching can be in the form of sermons or homilies, religious teachings, Catechesis for the people, prayers and worship, charitable works and social services, and preaching through Art and Music.

Karl Weick's organizational information theory is used as a guide in understanding the transformation of religious communication. Weick sees organizations as a system that receives various confusing and multi-interpretable information from its environment and tries to understand it (Morrison: 2021). The transformation of preaching in the Archdiocese of Ende reflects the sensemaking mechanism carried out by religious institutions when facing the uncertainty of the pandemic and digital change. The church, as an organization, makes strategic adaptations to simplify the complexity of communication through the digitalization of liturgy and

pastoral care, thereby minimizing ambiguity in conveying the message of faith.

In addition, in the digitalization framework, new media theory is used to see the phenomenon of using new media as a means of communication. According to Mc. Quail (in David et al., 2017), new media has the main characteristics of interrelated connectivity, providing access to individuals as recipients and senders of messages interactively, having various uses, and being open and accessible anywhere. According to Creeber & Martin in Feroza et al. (2020), new media is a communication product mediated by technology and integrated with digital computers. Its existence is able to overcome several limitations of previous conventional media, so that new media can be defined as an interactive communication media that operates with computer devices supported by an internet network. In this context, the congregation is not only a consumer of the message, but also participates in producing and distributing religious content. This creates a two-way communication dynamic that was previously rare in the church's hierarchical communication pattern. Thus, this theory is able to explain why digitalization has a broad impact on the structure and function of communication in the Church.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a qualitative method with a literature study approach or literature analysis. This approach was chosen because the main focus of the study is to examine and deeply understand the phenomenon of digital dialectics in religious preaching through tracing relevant written sources. Literature studies allow researchers to examine theories, data, and previous research results regarding the transformation of religious communication in a digital context, especially within the scope of the Catholic Church.

The data sources in this study consist of various academic literature such as books, scientific journals, digital articles, Church documents, and official publications and especially the YouTube channel Komsos Agung Ende and the YouTube channel Komsos SVD. related to religious preaching and the development of digital technology. Researchers also use digital documents such as recordings of online preaching, official Church social media content, and Church policies related to the use of digital media. These literatures are analyzed in depth to identify themes, patterns, and changes in the form of religious communication that occur due to digitalization.

The data analysis techniques used are content analysis and thematic analysis. This process involves data reduction steps, systematic data presentation, and drawing conclusions based on interpretations of the literature reviewed. The researcher seeks to uncover how digitalization creates new, more participatory forms of communication, and how religious values are renegotiated in the context of technology. Thus, this study is expected to provide theoretical contributions to the

Nikolaus Kristian B.R. et al, Digitalisation Dialectics in Religious Preaching: Analysis of Religious Communication Transformation in The Digital Era

study of contemporary religious communication and offer critical reflections on the digital proclamation strategy of the Catholic Church, especially in the Indonesian context.

IV. RESULTS

Covid-19 has become a major stepping stone in encouraging the use of digital media more massively, including in Church institutions. The transformation of religious proclamation from physical pulpits to digital screens marks more than just a change in medium, it reflects a new way for people to believe, convey, and receive spiritual messages in the digital era. In the context of the Archdiocese of Ende, the use of platforms such as YouTube to spiritual podcasts has complemented the function of the church pulpit and even more than that (in the form of spiritual activities and church life). Proclamation is now more flexible and accessible to the congregation, even to remote areas. This phenomenon supports the view of Hojsgaard and Warburg (2005), who stated that digitalization in the realm of religion has shifted religious activities from closed churches to more open public spaces. In this context, digital space acts as a modern altar where the congregation experiences faith through visual and auditory aspects.

In its depth, the Church faces not only challenges in adaptation, but also pros and cons regarding the utilization and effects caused. The existence of this conflict in the perspective of Karl Weick's organizational information theory, the church as an organizational system experiences information disorientation due to the pandemic and the pressure of digitalization. This situation creates a condition of "equivocality" (ambiguity of meaning) in communication, where various information comes from many directions, with a meaning that is not single (Morrison: 2021). The Church then carries out a "sensemaking" process to reorganize its understanding and communication strategy. This effort can be seen in the policy of using official digital channels (such as Komsos KAE and Komsos SVD), adjusting online liturgy, and digitalization training for pastoral staff.

The results of the study show a significant transformation in the practice of religious preaching in the Archdiocese of Ende due to digitalization. Proclamation, which previously focused on face-to-face communication in the form of mass, catechesis, and other pastoral activities, has now shifted to digital platforms such as social media, YouTube, WhatsApp, and the church's official website.

The main findings include: First, Use of Digital Platforms. The congregation and pastoral ministers actively utilize various digital platforms to disseminate religious content. Mass videos, daily devotions, and Bible reflections are broadcast online to reach congregations spread across a wide geographical area. Second, there are pros and cons related to efforts to adapt the use of digital media as a means of preaching. Third, Changes in Interaction Patterns. Interactions between priests and congregations become more interactive through

comments, personal messages, and participation in live streaming. This fosters a new form of virtual community of believers. Fourth, The Role of Spiritual Digital Influencers: Several priests and lay figures have become popular digital figures on social media because of the consistency and depth of their preaching. Their presence helps reach the younger generation who are more familiar with technology. Fifth, Challenges of Digitalization: Although it brings many benefits, digitalization also poses challenges, including the gap in access to technology in rural areas, the potential for theological disinformation, and the lack of digital literacy among pastoral ministers.

Based on the findings above, we can see that along with changes in media, there has also been a shift in the communicative relationship between Church leaders and the congregation. Digitalization accelerates the transformation of religious communication from a top-down monologic model to a participatory dialogic model. If previously the proclamation was one-way, from the priest to the congregation, now the digital space allows real-time interaction, comments, and participation of the congregation in content production. This situation reflects the democratization of religious communication as described by Habermas in Noor (2012) related to the public sphere that public space refers to conditions that facilitate citizens (in the private sphere) to unite to convey their aspirations, in order to form shared views and collective desires through a discursive process, which when associated with this research means that theological meanings are negotiated openly. However, this openness is not without risk: when individual opinions are no longer bound by the authoritative framework of the Church, interpretive chaos can arise. The Church is challenged to remain the main reference in the discourse of faith while opening up a healthy space for congregational participation.

V. DISCUSSION

The results of previous research studies show that although various previous studies have highlighted the role of digital media in strengthening social and spiritual values, such as tolerance (Abdullah, 2022) and the flexibility of the Church in responding to technology (Suhayardi et al., 2021; Yudha Nugraha, 2022), most have not discussed in depth the internal tensions between clerical authority and congregational participation that arise due to digitalization. Campbell's (2023) research strengthens this finding by showing the existence of technological resistance and infrastructure limitations in Africa, which were also experienced in Ende, indicating that the phenomenon of digital reluctance is a global problem. On the other hand, Cheong et al. (2012) and Cloete (2015) highlight changes in the structure of religious communities due to digital culture, but have not specifically examined how these dynamics affect the structure of Catholic preaching locally.

Setiawan's (2021) research on the role of YouTube in reaching the younger generation provides an important

contribution to understanding the effectiveness of digital media, which is also seen in the success of the KAE and SVD Komsos channels in Ende. However, this research goes beyond technical discussions by exploring the theological and pastoral dimensions of the use of digital media in preaching. Thus, this research fills the gap in academic discourse by highlighting the dialectic between traditional and digital preaching contextually. The constructivist approach used emphasizes that digitalization is not just a technological change, but an ideological process that requires the Church not to simply adapt, but to actively shape a relevant faith narrative in a complex and competitive digital landscape.

Dialectics of Transformation of News Media: From Pulpit to Screen

The transformation of religious communication in the context of the Archdiocese of Ende is a real reflection of a dialectical process as defined in Hegelian philosophy. Dialectics, in the Hegelian framework, moves in three main stages: thesis, antithesis, and synthesis. When the church is faced with the reality of digitalization, there is an encounter between the traditional values of preaching that have been rooted (thesis), with the challenges and opportunities brought by digital media (antithesis), which then encourages the birth of new forms of faith communication that are synthetic in nature.

As a hierarchical and liturgical religious institution, the Catholic Church has long relied on traditional forms of proclamation such as homilies, catechesis, mass, and face-to-face pastoral care. Interactions between people are passive and receptive, and values of faith are conveyed in sacred and physical spaces, such as the church or the catechesis classroom.

Traditional preaching in the Catholic Church has long roots in the culture of direct communication. This form is manifested in face-to-face Mass, homilies, catechesis, pastoral care, and the sacraments. This kind of communication does not only convey a verbal message, but is also loaded with symbolic meaning, affection, and spiritual closeness. The intimacy of this communication is strengthened by the physical presence that allows the congregation to see the expression of the preacher, feel the presence of the community, and experience directly the sacramental dimension of the preaching.

This model places interpersonal relations at the heart of preaching, where the preacher and the congregation are emotionally and spiritually involved. In mass, for example, the presence of the congregation allows for the creation of a concrete communion. Common prayer, liturgical singing, and holy communion can only be fully experienced within this physical and communitarian framework. Therefore, face-to-face communication becomes an inseparable part of the experience of the Catholic faith.

In this context, physical presence, ritual symbolism, and continuity of tradition are the main foundations in conveying religious messages. This communication pattern has the power to build deep emotional and spiritual attachments,

but is also limited in terms of space and time, especially for people who live in remote areas and are difficult to reach physically. In this context, the church often also positions the congregation as passive recipients of messages, because communication takes place in a linear and hierarchical manner.

Faced with digital proclamation, digitalization presents an antithesis to conventional proclamation patterns. Digital space, which is limitless, participatory, and easily accessible, demands the church to abandon one-way communication patterns and adopt more interactive, visual, and spontaneous communication. Social media, YouTube, WhatsApp, and other digital platforms are not only channels for spreading messages, but also form a new communication structure where people are no longer merely listeners, but producers and consumers of spiritual meaning.

Along with the development of digital technology and the acceleration that occurred during the COVID-19 pandemic, the Church began to turn to digital platforms such as YouTube to broadcast online masses, reflections, and other spiritual content. This digital proclamation allows the church to reach the congregation widely, without the limitations of space and time. The congregation can attend mass from home, access homily recordings at any time, and even interact through the comments column or live chat feature.

In this framework, communication becomes non-linear, decentralized, and individualistic. People do not need to be in church to experience the celebration of faith. Digital Mass becomes more flexible and efficient, especially for people in the diaspora, the sick, or those in emergency situations. YouTube allows the visualization of the message of faith in a creative, narrative, and contextual form, making it a very relevant medium for the younger generation.

Contextual and Transformative Digital Reporting

This dialectical process leads to a synthesis, namely the emergence of a new form of proclamation that combines aspects of traditional spirituality with innovative communicative approaches. In this context, the church does not simply "adopt technology", but transforms itself into a reflective and adaptive digital communicative actor.

The Church has the opportunity to embrace traditional and digital proclamation in a hybrid approach. The hybrid Mass model, which has begun to be implemented in the Diocese of Ende, allows a limited number of people to be physically present, while others follow online via live streaming. In this format, people can still participate symbolically through virtual offerings or sending prayers, without completely losing its spiritual dimension. This approach is in line with Hegel's dialectic theory, where the synthesis between two poles actually produces a new, more adaptive form.

To further deepen the concept above, Mystagogy; assistance in understanding the meaning of faith and sacraments can be expanded to the digital world. Catechesis podcasts, video narratives of scripture, or interactive quizzes

on social media can be effective means to reach the younger generation. This strategy not only creates engagement, but also opens up space for the internalization of faith values through culturally and technologically relevant media. So that real steps that can be taken include collaborating with internet service providers to build WiFi networks in remote churches, as well as forming digital missionary cadres from young people to help local communities access and understand the content of the proclamation.

Traditional and modern preaching are not two poles that must compete, but two approaches that must be integrated. The church needs to realize that the Gospel message is eternal, but its media must continue to be relevant. Digital preaching must not replace real communities, but rather lead to the formation of broader and more inclusive communities.

The synthesis between these two quite contrasting models of preaching can be done with a dual approach: equipping traditional preachers with digital literacy and at the same time equipping digital preachers with deep spirituality. The church can also form a "digital preaching team" that works with pastors and local preachers in compiling contextual and theological content. Thus, this study proposes that the Church needs to build digital literacy capacity for preachers, design theological guidelines for digital content production, and foster the involvement of the congregation so that they become critical and responsible consumers and producers of faith content. Digitalization does not mean throwing away the old, but rather combining it with a new approach that is in accordance with the digital culture of the congregation. In a pastoral context, this means building a preaching ecosystem that is collaborative, reflective, and relevant to the reality of today's congregation.

From all these findings, the researcher argues that digitalization is not a threat, but rather an opportunity to reconstruct the church's mission in facing an era that is constantly changing. This transformation needs to be read not merely as an adaptation to technological developments, but as a theological and pastoral process that demands openness and creativity from the entire church community. However, it is important to remember that the digital space is not value-free; behind the technology there are economic and ideological interests that can shape, even manipulate, messages of faith. Therefore, the Church is not enough to just be "present" in the digital space, but must be an active subject that shapes the digital consciousness of the people critically and responsibly.

The researcher also emphasized that the success of the transformation of religious communication is largely determined by the Church's readiness to read the cultural changes of the people. Technology is only a tool; the core of the proclamation remains dependent on the spiritual power of the community and the spirit of creative evangelization. In facing the digital world, the courage to present the Gospel in the "language of the times" is the main key so that the proclamation remains relevant and touches the reality of the

lives of the people. Thus, digitalization must be responded to not with fear, but with pastoral sensitivity, deep theological reflection, and a renewal of the paradigm of proclamation that is in favor of the people.

Future Prospects and Research Implications

Looking at the development of the transformation of religious communication studied in the Archdiocese of Ende, there is a possibility that trends will continue to develop in the future. First, the Hybrid Preaching Model and Flexible Liturgy. Preaching will increasingly move towards a hybrid model, namely the integration of traditional and digital preaching practices. Online and offline Masses, spiritual guidance through instant messaging platforms, and virtual retreats are formats that are predicted to continue to grow (Setiawan, 2021). Preaching becomes more flexible, reaching people who are geographically or socially difficult to be physically present. Second, Increasing Religious Digital Literacy and Infrastructure. In the future, religious digital literacy will be one of the main focuses. It is not enough to just master technology, preachers must also understand how to convey spiritual values relevantly in the digital space. This is in line with the findings of Cloete (2015), who emphasized the need for theological awareness of digital media so that spirituality does not get caught up in instant consumption.

Moreover, the Church's communication infrastructure will also be required to develop. Collaboration between the Church and digital service providers can be a strategic step to ensure inclusive access, especially in remote areas (Campbell, 2023). Finally, the Emergence of the Digital Preacher Generation. An interesting phenomenon that will grow is the emergence of the younger generation as digital preachers. They are not only consumers of faith content, but active producers who spread gospel values in innovative ways. This reflects the shift in the position of the preacher from a single authoritative figure to a collective and participatory one, as emphasized in the concept of networked individualism (Cheong et al., 2012).

This study provides academic contributions in two main aspects. First, Development of Contextual Religious Communication Studies. This study broadens the scope of religious communication studies by highlighting local dynamics (Archdiocese of Ende), which have tended to be neglected in global literature. This opens up space for further research based on other church contexts in Indonesia. Second, Contribution to the Study of Digital Transformation in Traditional Institutions. The church as a traditional institution is an ideal object for observing the dynamics of digital adaptation that is full of values and authority. This study is an important contribution to the fields of sociology of religion, organizational communication, and digital media studies.

Meanwhile, the practical implications of the results of this study can be utilized by Church actors and religious communities as a basis for developing relevant digital preaching strategies, for example in the design of digital

Nikolaus Kristian B.R. et al, Digitalisation Dialectics in Religious Preaching: Analysis of Religious Communication Transformation in The Digital Era

preaching training materials or guidelines for compiling digital content (based on an ethical and theological framework to ensure that digital content continues to prioritize the truth of faith and spiritual depth, not merely pursuing aesthetics or popularity).

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the entire contents of the document, it can be concluded that digitalization has created a profound transformation in the practice of religious proclamation, especially in the Archdiocese of Ende. The shift from traditional hierarchical and face-to-face communication patterns to a participatory digital model shows that the Catholic Church is facing a new reality in conveying the message of faith. Digital media such as YouTube, WhatsApp, and other social platforms have become new proclamation spaces that allow people, including those in remote areas, to stay spiritually connected. However, this transformation also poses various challenges, such as theological disinformation, digital literacy gaps, and shifts in religious authority that risk giving rise to interpretations that are not in line with the official teachings of the Church.

The synthesis of the digitalization dialectic in religious preaching shows that there needs to be a good adaptation from the Catholic Church. This adaptation can be in the form of a hybrid preaching model, digital literacy for preachers, and the active involvement of the congregation as content producers into forms of synthesis that answer the challenges of the times while maintaining spiritual depth. The church needs to be an active subject that is not only present digitally, but also forms the digital awareness of the congregation in a reflective and responsible manner. Thus, digitalization is not just a technical change, but a theological and pastoral process that opens up new opportunities to build a more inclusive, adaptive, and contextual community of faith.

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